
A Study on Performance Evaluation of Library Professionals in Engineering Colleges Affiliated To Visvesvaraya Technological University (VTU), Karnataka

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Abstract

The main objective of this study is the performance evaluation of library professionals working at engineering colleges affiliated with Visvesvaraya Technological University (VTU), Karnataka. The study emphasised factors influencing the performance of library professionals at their working place. The results of the study reveal that management's vision for improvement towards the library, adequate infrastructure, and sufficient allocation of the library budget influence the performance of librarians.

Keywords

Performance Appraisal; Library Professionals; Library Budget

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INTRODUCTION

Professional staff can be the most valuable resource in an effective academic library is certainly valid. While books, card catalogues, and other materials are essential components of a library, the expertise and skills of the professional staff play a crucial role in ensuring that these resources are effectively utilised and that the library meets the diverse needs of its users. In essence, the professional staff is the linchpin that connects the library's resources with the needs of its users (Adeniran, 2010). Their expertise in various areas ensures that the library is not just a repository of materials but a dynamic hub of information and support for the academic community. The dedication and proficiency of the professional staff contribute significantly to the overall effectiveness and impact of the library. By prioritising the training, motivation, and cooperation of library staff, administrators contribute significantly to the overall success of the library. A motivated and well-trained staff is better equipped to provide excellent service, adapt to changes, and contribute to the institution's goals. This, in turn, enhances the library's ability to offer total access to information and meet the evolving needs of its user community (Ikonne & Fajonyomi, 2019).

The library, as a tripartite organisation consisting of reference materials, users, and personnel, is a succinct and accurate description of the key components of a library. The interactions and relationships among these three components create the dynamic environment of the library. The library personnel act as intermediaries, connecting users with the vast array of reference materials available. Librarians, in particular, play a central role in assisting users with their information needs, guiding them in research, and promoting information literacy (Cobblah & Walt, 2017).

The role of motivation in employee performance is widely recognized in organizational management and psychology. Motivation refers to the internal and external factors that drive individuals to take action, put in effort, and achieve goals. Positive motivation involves providing employees with incentives, rewards, recognition, and a work environment that fosters a sense of accomplishment and job satisfaction (Hurque & Vyas, 2008). When employees are positively motivated, they are more likely to engage in their work, demonstrate commitment, and contribute to the success of the organization (Najafi et al., 2022). Positive motivation goes beyond just

improving individual performance; it profoundly impacts the overall well-being of employees and their connection to the organization. Positive motivation not only elevates individual performance but also has a cascading effect on the level of service provided to the clientele. Motivated employees are more likely to view customer service as a priority and actively contribute to creating positive and memorable experiences for the organization's clientele(Callahan & Watson, 1995).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Babaie-chamazkoti and Mokhtari (2016) conducted a study on the performance of public libraries in Golestan province, Iran, using the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) model. The study found that users' satisfaction with library services was satisfactory, while employees' satisfaction was average. However, Mir Findiriski Public Library had low internal processes and financial performance. Akbarnezhad & Dayyani (2019) evaluated the performance excellence of Iran's major public libraries using the Malcolm Baldrige Model.Machara & Jain (2016) found that librarians in Botswana were de-motivated and dissatisfied with their jobs due to job security, interpersonal relations, policies and procedures, working environment, benefits, and supervision. The study recommends that Botswana National Library Services management to adopt motivation theories, upgrade the library to fit a twenty-first-century environment, recognize employees appropriately for their work, provide adequate training and career development, create a conducive working environment, and implement proper policies and procedures.

Nwokike & Unegbu's (2019) study found that librarians performed at a high level on the job, suggesting regular training or skill acquisition. Muchinsky and Culbertson (2013) emphasised the importance of tracking and measuring employee behavior on the job as an accomplishment on a personal level. Okpe (2012) also highlighted the role of academic librarians in overseeing daily administration of learning resources, teaching, guiding users through instructions, and performing administrative tasks to maintain a supportive atmosphere for learning and teaching.

Amusa, Iyoro, and Ajani (2013) examined the work performance of librarians in Southwest Nigerian public universities. They found fair job performance based on factors including professional practice,

contribution to the library's general development, responsiveness to clients' requests, and fulfilment of minimum standards for advancement.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the performance of the library professionals.
2. To identify the factors influencing the performance of library professionals.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design:This study intends to use a descriptive survey design. The purpose of descriptive surveys is to collect detailed and factual information that describes an existing phenomenon.

Sapling Design:The study's target population will be the engineering colleges' library professionals of Visvesvaraya Technological University (VTU). The prepared questionnaire was distributed to about 280 Library professionals as part of the study. Of them, 266 library professionals gave responses.

Tool for Data Collection:The questionnaire method will be used to collect data from the respondents, and the interview method will also be used for the study. The study is mainly based on the primary data collected from the professionals working in different engineering college libraries affiliated with Visvesvaraya Technological University (VTU).

Data Analysis:The data collected for this research was coded and captured for analysis using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS).

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Table 1: Demographic Details of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	193	72.6
	Female	73	27.4
Domicile of the respondents	Urban	214	80.5
	Semi- Urban	12	4.5
	Rural	40	15.0
Age of the respondents	<- 30	57	21.4
	31-40	95	35.7
	41-50	75	28.2
	51-60	37	13.9

	61& above	2	0.8
Educational Qualification	Post Doctorate	10	3.8
	Doctorate (Ph.D.)	45	16.9
	M.Phil.	26	9.8
	Master's degree	149	56.0
	PG Diploma	9	3.4
	Bachelor's degree	27	10.2
Marital Status	Married	221	83.1
	Unmarried	41	15.4
	Widow/Widower	2	0.8
	Divorced	2	0.8
	Total	266	100

Table: 1 above describes the demographic details of the respondents. Out of 266 respondents, a majority of 72.6 per cent are male respondents. 27.4 per cent of them are female respondents. It is apparent from the above table that a majority, 72.6 per cent, of the respondents are male.

Out of 266 respondents, a majority, 80.5 per cent of the respondents belong to urban areas. 15.0 per cent of the respondents belong to rural areas. However, only 4.5 per cent of the respondents belong to semi-urban areas. It is apparent from the above table that a majority, 80.5 per cent, of the respondents belong to urban domicile.

Out of 266 of them, a majority, 35.7 per cent of the respondents, are between the age group of 31 – 40 years. A significant percentage of 28.2 % of respondents are between the age group of 41- 50 years. 21.4 per cent of the respondents are between the age group of more than 30 years. 13.9 per cent of the respondents are between the age group 51-60 years. Whereas, only 8 percent of the respondents are between the age group 61 years and above. It is apparent from the above table that the majority, 35.7 per cent of the respondents, are between the age group of 31-40 years.

Out of 266 respondents of them, a majority 56.0 per cent of the respondents are from Master's degree holders. 16.9 per cent of the respondents have a PhD (Doctor of Philosophy). 10.2 per cent of the respondents are bachelor's degree holders. 9.8 percent of the respondents have an M.Phil. (Master of Philosophy). 3.8 per cent of the respondents have a post-doctorate. Whereas only 3.4 per cent of the respondents have a PG diploma. It is apparent from the above table that the majority, 56 percent of the

respondents, are master's degree holders. Out of 266 respondents, a majority 83.1 percent of the respondents are married. A significant percentage of 15.4% of the respondents are unmarried. Whereas only 8 per cent of the respondents are widows/widowers and divorced.

It is apparent from the above table that the majority, 83.1 per cent of the respondents, are married.

Table 2: Performance appraisal reports are prepared

Performance Appraisal Reports are Prepared	Frequency	Percentage
Monthly	33	12.4
Quarterly	8	3.0
Half Yearly	14	5.3
Yearly	211	79.3
Total	266	100.0

Table 2 describes how the performance appraisal reports are prepared. Out of 266 respondents, a majority 79.3 percent of the respondents said that yearly they prepared performance appraisal reports. 12.4 per cent of the respondents said that they prepared appraisal reports monthly. 5.3 per cent of the respondents said that half-yearly, they prepared the performance appraisal reports. However, only 3.0 percent of the respondents said they prepared quarterly appraisal reports. It is apparent from the above table that the majority, 79.3 per cent of the respondent's performance appraisal report, are prepared yearly.

Table 3: Performance Appraisal is undertaken by

Undertaking responsibility of appraising	Frequency	Percentage
Superiors in the library	65	24.4
Committee	28	10.5
Outside experts	4	1.5
Head of the institution	169	63.5
Total	266	100.0

The table no: 3 describe that the who will undertake the responsibility of appraising to respondents. Out of 266 respondents, a majority 63.5 percent of the respondents said that the head of the institution is responsible for taking performance appraisal. Undertaken the responsibility. 24.4 percent of the respondents said that the superior in the library is undertaken the responsibility. 10.5 percent of the

respondents said that the committee is undertaken the responsibility. However, only 1.5 percent of the respondents said that outside experts are responsible. It is apparent from the above table that the majority of the respondents said that the head of the institution undertook the responsibility of the respondents.

Table 4: Management dedication and headship affecting the Performance of librarians by the respondents

Management Dedication and Headship	Very High	High	Normal	Low	Very Low
Management vision for improvement towards the library	168 (63.2)	56 (21.1)	34 (12.8)	6 (2.3)	2 (0.8)
Well-organized staffing process and encouragement	94 (35.3)	90 (33.8)	68 (25.6)	12 (4.5)	2 (0.8)
Association constitution and transparency in strategies	61 (22.9)	71 (26.7)	76 (28.6)	20 (7.5)	38 (14.3)
Headship and inspirational plans	83 (31.2)	69 (25.9)	62 (23.3)	20 (7.5)	32 (12.0)
Decentralization and contribution of library staff	108 (40.6)	66 (24.8)	60 (22.6)	20 (7.5)	12 (4.5)

The above table no: 4 depicts the critical factors affecting on Performance of librarians by the respondents. Out of 266 respondents, majority 63.2 percent of the respondents said that management vision for improvement towards library affects very high on performance of librarians and 0.8 percent of the respondents said that management vision for improvement towards library affects very low on performance of librarians. 35.3 percent of the respondents said that well-organized staffing process and encouragement affects very high on performance of librarians and 0.8 percent of the respondents said that well-organized staffing process and encouragement affects very low on performance of librarians.

26.7 per cent of the respondents said that the Association constitution and transparency in strategies affect the performance of librarians, and 7.5 per cent of the respondents said that the Association

constitution and transparency in strategies affect the performance of librarians. 31.2 per cent of the respondents said that headship and inspirational plans affect the performance of librarians, and a very small 7.5 per cent of the respondents said that headship and inspirational plans affect the very low performance of librarians. 40.6 per cent of the respondents accepted that decentralisation and contribution of library staff affect the performance of librarians, and 4.5 per cent of the respondents said that decentralization and contribution of library staff affect the very low performance of librarians.

Table 5: Financial Assets affecting the Performance of librarians

Financial Assets	Very High	High	Normal	Low	Very Low
Sufficient money spent on books etc. per resident per year	112 (42.1)	100 (37.6)	50 (18.8)	2 (0.8)	2 (0.8)
Allocate sufficient budget per year for maintaining and up gradation of library	61 (22.9)	102 (38.3)	49 (18.4)	26 (9.8)	28 (10.5)
Financial resources for training and up gradation of library staff	45 (16.9)	89 (33.5)	68 (25.6)	37 (13.9)	27 (10.2)
Sufficient budget for maintaining stock of books, journals, magazines and other materials	96 (36.1)	79 (29.7)	42 (15.8)	16 (6.0)	33 (12.4)
Sufficient non-recurring budget	64 (24.1)	81 (30.5)	77 (28.9)	20 (7.5)	24 (9.0)

The above table no: 5 describes how financial assets affect the performance of librarians. Out of 266 respondents. Of the, the majority, 42.1 per cent of the respondents said that sufficient money spent on books, etc., affects the performance of librarians, and a very low 0.8 per cent of the respondents marked

that sufficient money spent on books affects low and very low performance of librarians.38.3 per cent of the respondents mentioned that a sufficient budget per year affected the maintenance and gradation of librarians' performances, and 9.8 per cent of the respondents mentioned that a sufficient budget per year affected low maintenance and upgradation of librarians' performance.

33.5 per cent of the respondents said that financial resources for the training and gradation of library staff affect the performance of librarians, and 10.2 per cent of the respondents said that financial resources for training and gradation of library staff affect the performance of librarians.36.1 per cent of the respondents said that a sufficient budget for maintaining libraries affects the performance of librarians, and a very small 6.0 per cent of the respondents stated that a budget for maintaining libraries affects librarians' performance. 30.5 per cent of the respondents noted that a sufficient non-recurring budget highly affects the performance of librarians, and 7.5 per cent of the respondents mentioned that a sufficient non-recurring budget affects the performance of librarians.

Table 6: Physical Infrastructure affecting on Performance of librarians with Physical Infrastructure

Physical Infrastructure	Very High	High	Normal	Low	Very Low
Comfort, suitability and appeal of library building for purpose	120 (45.1)	86 (32.3)	40 (15.0)	14 (5.3)	6 (2.3)
Availability and accessibility of internet facility and library building	92 (34.6)	84 (31.6)	48 (18.0)	22 (8.3)	20 (7.5)
Convenience of library building location in college	91 (94.2)	77 (28.9)	32 (12.0)	32 (12.0)	34 (12.8)
Provision of power backup in library	116 (43.6)	66 (24.8)	38 (14.3)	24 (9.0)	22 (8.3)
Seating and storage capacity of library	112 (42.1)	72 (27.1)	36 (13.5)	22 (8.3)	24 (9.0)

The above table no: 6 describes how physical infrastructure affects on performance on librarians. Out of 266 respondents. Of them majority 45.1 percent of the respondents said that Comfort, suitability and appeal of library building affects very high on performance of librarians and 2.3 percent of the respondents said that Comfort, suitability and appeal of library building affects very low on performance of librarians.34.6 percent of the respondents said that Availability and accessibility of internet facility and library building affects very high on performance of librarians and 2.3 percent of the respondents said that Availability and accessibility of internet facility and library building affects very low on performance of librarians.34.3 percent of the respondents noted that Convenience of library building location in college affects very high on performance of librarians. A small 12.0 per cent of the respondents said that the Convenience of library building location in college affects the performance of librarians.

The majority, 43.6 percent of the respondents, noted that the Provision of power backup in a library affects the performance of librarians, and 8.3 percent of the respondents mentioned that the Provision of power backup in a library affects the performance of librarians. Majority 42.1 percent of the respondents noted that Seating and storage capacity of library affects very high on performance of librarians and 8.3 percent of the respondents mentioned that Seating and storage capacity of library affects low on performance of librarians.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- It is found from the study is that the majority of respondents were male, i.e. 72.6%, whereas females 27.4%.
- The study also showed that the majority (80.5%) of the respondents belonged to urban areas, and only 15% per cent of the respondents belonged to rural areas.
- It is observed that more than 60% of respondents lie in the age group of 31-50 years, which indicates that the majority of respondents were young by age.
- The study reveals that out of 266 respondents, 56% of the respondents have a Master's degree, and 16.9 per cent of the respondents have a PhD degree. It indicates that the majority of respondents have better qualifications to execute their duties.

- The majority of respondents (79.3%) expressed that they are preparing performance appraisal reports yearly.
- The study indicated that the majority of the respondents said that the head of the institution undertook the responsibility of appraising the respondents.
- The study showed that financial stability and allocation of sufficient budget for information resources, library up-gradation and training are the major factors, which influence the performance of librarians.
- The study also opined that adequate infrastructure facilities such as library buildings, ICT facilities, building locations, UPS and comfortable furniture also influence the performance of librarians.

CONCLUSION

It's important to note that the assessment of job performance can vary based on the criteria used and the context of the study. The positive findings in this particular study may reflect the dedication, skills, and commitment of librarians in the engineering colleges of Karnataka during the time of the investigation. Performance evaluation should not only measure individual or team achievements but also critically assess whether the activities being undertaken align with organizational goals and contribute meaningfully to success. Regularly reviewing the appropriateness of activities ensures that the organization remains agile, responsive, and focused on achieving its overarching mission.

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